

netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society

Inclusion Report 3

WP2_D2.4

H2020-SC6-REV-INEQUAL-2016

Grant Agreement number: 727066

1st November 2018 – 30th October 2019

Inclusion Report 3

Deliverable number WP2_D2.4

Deliverable description			
Filename	WYRED_WP2_D 2.4v1.pdf		
Type	R		
Dissemination level	PU		
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.3564918		
Due Date (in months)	M36		
Deliverable contributors			
Version No.	Name, Institution	Role	Last update
V.01	MOVES	Author	30.10.2019
V.02	MOVES	Author	14.11.2019
V.03	MOVES	Author	18.11.2019
V.04	All Partners	Contributions to D2.2	02.12.2019
V.1	Zauchner-Studnicka, S. MOVES	Final Version	03.12.2019

* cfr. GA – Annex I Part A – 1.3.2 WT2 – list of deliverables

Table of Contents

Tables and Figures	5
1 Inclusion in WYRED	6
1.1 Understanding of Inclusion and Diversity	6
1.2 Deliverable Objectives	7
2 Analyses	9
2.1 Platform Data (Inclusion Questionnaire)	9
2.1.1 Gender	10
2.1.2 Age	11
2.1.3 Education and Work Background	11
2.1.4 Socio-Economic Status (SEC)	14
2.1.5 Geographic Location	15
2.1.6 Migration	16
2.1.7 Ethnic/National Background	17
2.1.8 Religion	18
2.1.9 Disability	19
2.1.10 Sexual Orientation	20
2.2 Data from Partners	21
1.1.1 Austria	21
1.1.2 Belgium	22
1.1.3 Israel	22
1.1.4 Italy	23
1.1.5 Northern Ireland	23
1.1.6 Spain	23
1.1.7 Turkey	24
1.1.8 United Kingdom	24
3 Conclusions	25
4 References	29
5 Glossary of Terms	33
6 Appendix	35

Inclusion Report 3
WP2_D2.4

6.1	Inclusion Questionnaire	35
6.2	Inclusion Template	37

Tables and Figures

<i>Table 1: Versions of the Inclusion Questionnaire (IQ) used in WYRED</i>	7
<i>Figure 1: Percentage of IQs related to total participants (own source, 2019)</i>	9
<i>Figure 2: Gender ratio - IQ participants (own source, 2019)</i>	10
<i>Figure 3: Interrelation between Gender and Age - IQ participants (own sources, 2019)</i>	10
<i>Figure 4: Age-categories - IQ participants (own source, 2019)</i>	11
<i>Figure 5: ISCED levels in WYRED – IQ participants (own source, 2018)</i>	12
<i>Figure 6: Students in formal education - IQ participants (own source, 2019)</i>	13
<i>Figure 7: Activities apart from formal education - IQ participants (own source, 2019)</i>	14
<i>Figure 8: Socio Economic Status (SEC) - IQ participants (own source, 2019)</i>	14
<i>Figure 9: Place of residence - IQ participants (own source, 2019)</i>	15
<i>Figure 10: Place of work or study - IQ participants (own source, 2019)</i>	16
<i>Figure 11: Migration background - IQ participants (own source, 2019)</i>	16
<i>Figure 12: Ethnic Groups in WYRED - IQ participants (own source, 2019); without Turkey</i>	17
<i>Figure 13: Religion in WYRED - IQ participants (own source, 2019); without Turkey</i>	19
<i>Figure 14: Active Members in Religion - IQ participants (own source, 2019); without Turkey</i>	19
<i>Figure 15: Disability or long-term illness - IQ participants (own source, 2019)</i>	20
<i>Figure 16: Sexual orientation - IQ participants (own source, 2019); without Turkey</i>	20

1 Inclusion in WYRED

1.1 Understanding of Inclusion and Diversity

The WYRED project (García-Peñalvo, 2017, 2018; García-Peñalvo & García-Holgado, 2019; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016; Griffiths et al., 2017) is informed by the recognition that young people of all ages have the right for participation and engagement in the digital world. It has a strong focus on inclusion, diversity and the empowerment of the marginalised, which is realized in Work Package 2 “Inclusion” - in its transversal function covering the whole project.

Inclusion in WYRED is committed to an understanding of diversity that regards differences as normal and values the idea of anyone equally participating in all aspects of life and decision-making. As a sociological term, inclusion indicates a society in which every person is accepted and regarded as equal and self-determined, irrespective of specific individual diversity criteria. Differences between individuals are regarded as an enrichment and as being normal. Inclusion values equality and equal participation of every member of society in all aspects of life, including civic, social, economic, and political activities, as well as decision-making processes. Regarding differences as being normal is the most essential proposition in the model of inclusion.

The inclusion process was an integral part of the whole work process and it accompanied WYRED from the very beginning to even beyond the end of the project and the success of the project was closely related to WYRED’s theoretical understanding and practical implementation of inclusion. Inclusion criteria were selected within the 1st project cycle based upon the internationally well-known diversity criteria Gender, Age, Education, Socio-Economic Status, Migration, Ethnic/National Background, Geographic Location, Disability, Religion and Sexual Orientation (Abdul-Hussain & Baig, 2009; Loden & Rosener, 1991). Within the 1st and 2nd cycles criteria were continuously adapted to the outcomes of discussions with partners, their

feedback and specific cultural needs. Last this was done in September 2018, when suggestions for the adaptation of the two questions about the ethnic/national background and religion were made by the lead partner and intensely discussed by the partners. This resulted into the final version of the questionnaire, implemented in October 2018, and used within cycle 3. During these processes it also turned out that cultural adaptations needed to be done which means, that in the last research cycle four versions of the inclusion questionnaire (IQ) were implemented on the platform (Table 1).

<p>Version 1 IQ for participants \geq 18 years. This questionnaire contains all diversity criteria as indicated above. It implements the gender question in the version of asking for gender transition.</p>	<p>Version 2 IQ for participants $<$ 18 years. This questionnaire contains all diversity criteria except the sexual orientation question and applies a simple version of asking for the genders (just male, female).</p>
<p>Version 3 IQ for participants \leq 14 years. This questionnaire differs from version 2 only in the introduction, which is written in an easier understandable language for the younger participants of WYRED.</p>	<p>Version 4 IQ for Turkish participants The Turkish partner used an individual questionnaire which applies the simple gender question, as well as the questions for age, education, social economic status, migration, geographic location, and disability.</p>

Table 1: Versions of the Inclusion Questionnaire (IQ) used in WYRED

During the course of the project the partners were continuously informed about the status quo of inclusion in D1.1., D2.2 and D2.3, after the midterm evaluation in January 2018 as well as at the regular project meetings.

1.2 Deliverable Objectives

The present deliverable D2.4 is the final WP2 inclusion report in WYRED. It is based on D2.1 v.2 (August 2017) "Inclusion criteria" (Zauchner-Studnicka, 2017) and D2.2. "Inclusion report" (December 2017) (Zauchner-Studnicka, 2018a) and D2.3 "Inclusion report" (October 2018) (Zauchner-Studnicka, 2018b).

While D2.1 was technically oriented, providing the consortium with practical information about how to efficiently implement the individual criteria in their countries, D2.2 focused on the WYRED experiences with implementing inclusion criteria in the first research cycle and the partners' definition of minority groups in their countries. D2.3 continued the process

Inclusion Report 3
WP2_D2.4

including the constantly growing numbers of participants filling in the inclusion questionnaire on the WYRED platform.

The present report D2.4 goes beyond, as it includes all cycles and all WYRED participants, which means also the ones who did not fill in the inclusion questionnaire. Using a simple template (see 6.2) based on the questionnaire (see 6.1), these data were provided by the consortium partners respectively by the facilitators working with the children or young people in the three cycles.

2 Analyses

2.1 Platform Data (Inclusion Questionnaire)

Data from all platform (García-Holgado & García-Peñalvo, 2018; García-Peñalvo & Durán-Escudero, 2017; García-Peñalvo, García-Holgado, Vázquez-Ingelmo, & Seoane-Pardo, 2018; García-Peñalvo, Vázquez-Ingelmo, & García-Holgado, 2019; García-Peñalvo, Vázquez-Ingelmo, García-Holgado, & Seoane-Pardo, 2019) users younger than 30 years registered on October 31st, 2019 were used for analyses, which are 385 children and young people.

As can be seen in Figure 1, the percentage of participants registered on the platform and filling in the inclusion questionnaire was relatively stable in the run of the project and ranged from 47 % in December 2017 to 57 % in March 2018. The high percentage of 71 % in November 2017 was due to the fact that we had defined the questionnaire as being compulsory, which turned out to be a hindrance for the registration process. We therefore decided to remind the participants to complete the questionnaire as soon as being registered on the platform. This was done as well by the facilitators as by an invitation in the Welcome Community and lead to the rise of 10 % from November 2017 to March 2018.

Figure 1: Percentage of IQs related to total participants (own source, 2019)

During the project the percentage was consistently over 50 % and at the official end of the project on October 31st, 2019 the rate of questionnaires completed in relation to total registered users under the age of 30 was exactly 54,45 %. This can be regarded as a satisfactory return rate. In the following this group of WYRED participants is subsumed under the term "IQ participants".

2.1.1 Gender

About two thirds of the IQ participants are female (Figure 2). Relating this result to the share of the genders in the different age-groups (Figure 3), it can be seen that especially the age group from 20 to 24 years with 118 females and 33 males is unequally distributed – this also accounts for the age group from 25 to 29 years (34 females; 19 males) – while the other age groups are quite equal in regard to the genders. Partly the unequal distribution can be explained by the age shift of the IQ participants, as in 2018 the number of females in the age group of 15 to 19 years was 92 and that of males was 52. Though, it also speaks for a gender bias in the academic subjects of the IQ participants, respectively in the organisations selected for collaboration.

Figure 2: Gender ratio - IQ participants (own source, 2019)

Figure 3: Interrelation between Gender and Age - IQ participants (own sources, 2019)

2.1.2 Age

The WYRED age groups for children and young people apply to the European definition of youth (Statistical Office of the European Communities, 2015). Over the whole process of the project, the age groups 15 to 19 and 20 to 24 were covered most. With 41 IQ participants in 2019 we were successful in giving more attention to the age-group from 10 to 14 which showed only one IQ participant in 2018.

Figure 4: Age-categories - IQ participants (own source, 2019)

Still, the different numbers in the age groups may be a result of easy access to participants or organisations, as well might be due to the assessment that the WYRED methodology is more usable for the older age groups than for the younger.

2.1.3 Education and Work Background

The educational respective the work background criterion is based upon three distinctive questions.

All participants were asked for their educational level (ISCED), which is shown in

Figure 5. In most European countries, compulsory education lasts until 15 to 16 years, in several countries even until 18 – which is covered by ISCED (International Standard Classification of Education) level 2 and 3 (European Commission, 2016). In line with the age structure, most participants are on a Secondary II level (ISCED 3), followed by Bachelor level (ISCED 6), Primary Level (ISCED 1), Secondary I (ISCED 2), Post-secondary non-tertiary education (ISCED 4), Short Tertiary Education (ISCED 5) and Master level (ISCED 7). Three IQ participants have not completed primary school yet and there are 2 IQ participants on doctoral level.

Figure 5: ISCED levels in WYRED – IQ participants (own source, 2018)

It seems clear, that an equal share of all the ISCED categories can't be the aim of the project, especially regarding ISCED 4 to 8. ISCED 3 currently seems to be fed to a high extent by the age group of 15-19.

85 % of the IQ participants are engaged in formal education as shown in

Figure 6.

Figure 6: Students in formal education - IQ participants (own source, 2019)

Instead they are employed or self-employed, are having internships, and some are attending non-formal education (Figure 7). Five IQ participants are engaged in more than one of these activities.

Figure 7: Activities apart from formal education - IQ participants (own source, 2019)

2.1.4 Socio-Economic Status (SEC)

Socio-economic status (SEC) in WYRED is calculated by an indicator derived from the educational status of both, the participant's father and mother (mean). This simply calculated factor must be considered with care, as usually SEC is derived from the three factors educational level, family income and parents' occupation. As well the latter two primary factors as other secondary factors were not applied, primarily because SEC-indices are often criticised in terms that young people cannot answer correctly, as they simply do not know the data – especially regarding family income. Also, an often-applied secondary indicator - number of books in a household – must be criticised in regard to validity when considering the rising use of digital media for reading books.

Figure 8: Socio Economic Status (SEC) - IQ participants (own source, 2019)

Therefore, SEC is categorised as follows: Low: ISCED 0-2; Medium: ISCED 3-5; High: ISCED: 6-8, which as planned in the benchmarks brings the picture of the highest proportion for medium SES.

2.1.5 Geographic Location

Geographic location makes a difference. This may account for differences in the availability of educational (Ortlieb & Cheek, 2008) or health-systems (e.g. Chan, Hart, & Goodman, 2006) on the countryside and in smaller or bigger towns. It also may account for the development of technological infrastructure as broadband internet access (Whitacre & Mills, 2007) or the expansion of the public transport respectively the road network. Also, for example the development of ventures may differ relating to geographic location (e.g. Fernhaber, Gilbert, & McDougall, 2008).

When considering IQ participants place of residence, data reveal on the one hand that slightly more IQ participants stem from villages, small and middle towns as related to big towns (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Place of residence - IQ participants (own source, 2019)

Secondly it is seen that several inhabitants of villages and small towns are moving to big towns to study or for work (Figure 10) which as stated above reflects missing infrastructure in rural areas and might be perceived as disadvantageous.

Figure 10: Place of work or study - IQ participants (own source, 2019)

2.1.6 Migration

Migration is well reflected in WYRED. According to Eurostat (2017) there were 35,1 million people born outside of the EU-28 living in an EU Member State on January 1st 2016, which is 6,9% of the total population, while there were 19,3 million persons who had been born in a different EU Member State from the one where they were resident (3,8%). 1st generation migrants in WYRED (as defined by birth places of the participants and their parents as well as the main spoken language in the family) have a share of 7,27 %, 1st and 2nd generation migrants counted together make up 10,91 %, including one parent being migrant the ratio is 15,58 %.

Figure 11: Migration background - IQ participants (own source, 2019)

2.1.7 Ethnic/National Background

Data show a broad spectrum of ethnic groups in the different partner countries. These were analyzed by comparing the countries where the participants live, and the ethnic or national background stated. Whereas 47 % participants did not answer this question, 41 % belong to the majority groups like having Italian ethnicity in Italy and 12 % are representing minority groups. This means, that they identify with another nationality or an ethnic group of another country respectively a national ethnic group. The latter was especially seen in Spain, where Basques, Catalan, Andalusian, Galician, Valencian, and Mallorquin ethnicity are stated. Besides Flemish, also Indian Traveller and Bambara (an ethnic Group in South-East Mali) are named.

Figure 12: Ethnic Groups in WYRED - IQ participants (own source, 2019); without Turkey

As for Austria mainly ethnicities from the Balkan states, like Bosnian, Croat, Serbian are mentioned as well as Czech and Italian. In Italy Wolof (a language spoken in Senegal) Romani and Ukrainian ethnicity and in the UK Afro-Caribbean and Asian ethnicity is stated. As for the partner countries Northern Ireland and Belgium, it is mainly the national ethnicity the IQ participants tell us, for the British partners it is Afro-Caribbean and Asian ethnicity which is mentioned. Turkey had skipped this question.

Several times two ethnicities are mentioned like Spanish and British in Spain or Austrian and Serbian in Austria. One participant from Portugal¹ topped this with his ethnicity being Ukrainian, Russian, Polish and Tatar. The partition of Cyprus is reflected in identifying as being a Turkish or being a Geek Cypriot.

Operationalizing this question in form of an international list of ethnic groups worked less well than the open question used before (2018: 40% giving no answer). Considering that the county lists we displayed were heavily used, the high rate of non-respondents might be attributed to the fact, that the majority groups, like living in Austria and having an Austrian ethnicity, did not see the need to fill in their nationality again. Thus, one further final adaptation was made to the IQ questionnaire which means that we will return to the open question again.

2.1.8 Religion

With the adaptation of the question of adherence to a religious group, the high rate of IQ participants of 37,34 % not answering in 2018 was reduced to 21,07 % in 2019. Still, this is the second highest rate of giving no answer in the questionnaire.

About 75 % of the European people are Christians (mainly catholic, but also protestant and orthodox), 6 to 8 % are Muslims and about 0,3 % Jews. About one third of the Europeans describe themselves as irreligious (which means that they do not adhere to a religious group) and 5 % as atheistic (which means that they do not believe in god²).

Our sample consist of 55.03 % Christians, 8.94 % Muslims, 1.57 % Jews, 3.77 % adhere to another religion and 10.06 % are not believing or atheists. If Turkey had participated in this question, of course a higher share of Muslims would be given.

¹ The partner PYE involved several participants from beyond the partner countries.

² <https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Europa>

Figure 13: Religion in WYRED - IQ participants (own source, 2019); without Turkey

More than one third of the IQ participants are active members of one of the above shown religions (¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.).

Figure 14: Active Members in Religion - IQ participants (own source, 2019); without Turkey

2.1.9 Disability

Regarding the involvement of disabled children or young people respectively participants with a long-term illness, equal to 2008 5 % of respondents can be subsumed to this category. According to the benchmarks as specified in D.2.1., the benchmark for Europe lies at about 15 %, though it must be considered that this accounts for the whole European population and not solely for the young.

Figure 15: Disability or long-term illness - IQ participants (own source, 2019)

2.1.10 Sexual Orientation

The sexual orientation question was displayed to 218 participants older than 18 years. Interestingly for this question there were far less persons (5 %) not answering the question, than the questions for religion. The share of homo- as well as bisexual persons both lies at 5 % which is well expected regarding the defined benchmark-range of in between 1 to 10 percent.

Figure 16: Sexual orientation - IQ participants (own source, 2019); without Turkey

2.2 Data from Partners

Whereas 708 users younger than 30 years are registered on the WYRED platform, 385 added their data to the inclusion questionnaire. Still, this does not tell the whole story of inclusion in WYRED, as for example numerous participants did not register on the platform for various reasons like being engaged in online dialogues outside the platform, for technical availability of computers, technical skills of the participants, the secure registration process demanding an e-mail account or time restriction especially in schools. Therefore, for this final report, on the last project meeting in September 2019, we decided to include diversity data from all participants involved into the activities in the partner countries. A simple template (see 6.2) was provided for the partners respectively the facilitators within the research cycles to characterize the young people they had worked with.

1.1.1 Austria

In Austria in total 108 young people were involved in WYRED. Their ages ranged from 14 to 22 years and MOVES worked together with different types of schools respectively organizations: An occupational Secondary II School focused on Economy and Tourism (Hertha Firnberg Schulen, HFB) – a demanding school as it is finishing with ISCED 5. Further, with a Secondary I School working with disadvantaged young people (Center for Inclusive Schools CIS, ISCED 2) and an organization preparing school-leavers for an apprenticeship (Produktionsschule Eggenburg PE, ISCED 1-2). The first and the second schools are located in Vienna and the third in Lower Austria in a small town.

The gender share in CIS and PE was equal, whereas in HFB, more females participated in the project. This is due to the school type, attracting more young women than men. Whereas chronic illness or disability was no issue in HFB, both CIS and PE had a very high rate of about 30%. With 80% 1st and 2nd generation migration was a big topic in CIS as well as for HFB with 30%, interestingly it was much lower in PE (5%), which can be explained by the fact, that Vienna as being a big town attracts more migrants than the countryside. Socio-economic level was low for PE and CIS, middle for HFS. Major religion was Catholic, in CIS also Muslim. Minority groups in HFB mainly stemmed from Serbia and Croatia, also from India and Ghana, in CIS only four of the 19 participants had Austrian ethnicity the others stated Serbian (4), Turkish (2), Afghan (2), Syriac (2) Kurdish (2), Croatian (1), Chechen (1) and Russian (1).

1.1.2 Belgium

YEU as an international organization had a different way of engaging young people which mainly was involving them into online conversations. In doing this, they collaborated with several Youth organizations like MOJU, YEUE Cyprus, Active Bulgarian Society, USB, TOG, DYPALL, La Fenice, Project2020, Act for Change, CID, RCLE, CIM Horizonty, IUS, FRI.³

In total 412 young people participated in the YEUE activities – out of them 57 in face to face workshops (in two big towns, one medium and one small town) and 355 in online discussions. ISCED 3, 4 and 6 were covered, age ranged from 10 years to 29. Slightly more females (53,2 %) than males (46,8 %) participated in the dialogues. 15 Syrian refugees took part in the activities, there is no information available about 2nd generation migrants. Ethnicity – in this case understood as nationality of the participants – was extremely diverse: Belgian (29,1 %), Italian (25,5 %), Greek (6,8 %), British (6,1 %), Spanish (5,8 %), Turkish (5,6 %), Macedonian (5,1 %), Portuguese (4,1 %), Syrian (3,6 %), Ukrainian (3,6 %), Bulgarian (2,8 %) and Serbian (1,7 %). The share of homosexuals of the YEUE participants was 7,8 percent.

1.1.3 Israel

Israel involved 174 young people aged 16 to 17 years from the Science oriented youth programme (“Alpha program”) and also participants from the Summer Youth University of Tel Aviv University. Further, young people from “Hof Hasharon” High School and “Har Vagai” High school participated in WYRED, both located in rural areas.

Israel turns out to be the only partner having a higher share of male participants (59,2 %) than females 40,8 %). Eight percent were 1st generation migrants, approximately 20 % were 2nd generation migrants. All participants were in formal training and on ISCED level 3 and all categories (low, medium, high) of socio-economic status were covered. In regard to ethnicity mostly Israeli Jews with various ethnic backgrounds attended. Religion was mainly

³ MOJU - Association – Movimento Juvenil em Olhão; USB - United Societies of Balkans; TOG - Toplum Gönüllüleri Vakfı; DYPALL - Developing Youth Participation at Local Level; CID - Centre for Intercultural Dialogue; RCLE - Resource Centre Leskovac; CIM Horizonty - Centrum Inicjatyw Młodzieżowych HORYZONTY; IUS - Institute for Ukrainian Studies; FRI - Foundation of Regional Initiatives.

Jewish – it is estimated by the facilitator, that about nine to eleven percent of the participants were Muslims respectively Druze.

1.1.4 Italy

In Italy, Oxfam implemented project activities with 30 young people, working in collaboration with Roma Tre University, Sapienza University, ITT Cristoforo Colombo high school and Scup – Sport e Cultura Popolare social centre. The Italian partners empowered two thirds of their participants in their academic careers supporting their bachelor or master theses, which was highly time-consuming.

In general, 23.3 % were males and 76.6 % were females. In terms of ethnicity, 97% of participants were Italian. Regarding the age groups 26% were between 15 and 19 years old, while 74% were between 20 and 24 years old. Concerning geographical distribution 21% came from rural areas while 79% came from the city of Rome. ISCED Level was 5 at the Universities and 3 at the High School and the social centre.

1.1.5 Northern Ireland

In Northern Ireland the partner Early Years involved Augher Youth Club, Recarson Primary School, the Killyclogher Primary School and the Omagh Integrated Primary School, located in a small as well as in a medium town. They reached 158 children with their activities.

This means that all their participants were younger than 11 years of age and ISCED 1 was addressed. The share of the genders was 55 % female and 45 % male. First generation migrants as well as 2nd generation migrants made up 5,7 % of the participants. Socio-economic status was diverse – low, medium and high. According ethnicity 72,8 % were Irish, 20,3 % British, 5,7 % Eastern European and 1,2 % Chinese. The major part of the children was roman catholic (77 %) and 23 % were protestant. As related to the platform statistics a high rate of 12 % was chronically ill or had a disability.

1.1.6 Spain

Spain involved 223 young people from University of Salamanca, I.E.S. Venancio Blanco, English Academy GO KIDS, and the Public-School San Mateo, all located in Salamanca.

The ages of the participants ranged from 12 to 29 years, still there are five young people who had joined the project during the 1st cycle with 27-29 years, and now they are over 30. Regarding the educational context, most of the participants attended formal training, except children of the English School GO KIDS, who attended non-formal training as well as formal

training. Therefore, a broad spectrum of the ISCED levels was covered: 1, 2, 3, 6 and 7. Regarding gender, 72,2 % of the participants were female, 26,9 % male, and there is 0,45 % who consider non-binary, and 0,45 % that preferred not to answer the gender question. The imbalance according to gender is due to the fact, that the faculty of education, where the general share of females is over 70%, was involved into the WYRED activities.

Further, most of the participants were Spaniards and some – as already stated before - indicated to be Andalusians, Catalans, Galicians, Cantabrian, Valencians, and Majorcan. Finally, considering religion, 10,31% were atheist or agnostic, 25,11% were Catholics, 0,9% were orthodox, 0,45% were Muslim - the other participants did not provide this information.

1.1.7 Turkey

Turkey involved 349 young people from Atasehir 1, Beykoz, Gaziantep, Mavisehir 1 and Antalya Doga Schools as well from Bilgi University.

The ages of the participants ranged from 10 to 29 years. All participants attended formal training, therefore – like in Spain – a broad spectrum of ISCED levels was covered: 1, 2, 3, 6, and 7. The gender share was 63 % of the participants female and 37 % male. Considering the socio-economic level 90 % of the participants were medium and 10 % low. They mainly stemmed from the Turkish majority group, 15 participants had Irish, Greek or Portuguese ethnicity.

1.1.8 United Kingdom

Boundaries worked with 73 young people, out of them 57 from the British School Croydon in London (cycle 1 and 2) and in cycle 1 with 16 young people from different affiliations and varies regionality.

The majority was female (55), 18 participants were male and two had selected the other category. The percentage of 2nd generation migrants was 32%, they attended formal training on ISCED 3 level, the socio-economic status was medium for all participants in the British School. There there were no migrants in cycle 1, the participants had ISCED 3 and 2 and the socio-economic status was medium to high. The ethnic background of the participants in cycle 1 was Caucasian, in the British school Croydon it was very diverse – whereas about 43 % of the participants were part of the majority group, about 45% were Afro-Caribbean and about 12% Asian. One participant was autistic, and one was deaf. Nine participants were homosexual, 64 were heterosexual.

Inclusion Report 3 WP2_D2.4

Further in cycle 2, 70 young people from a home educated group in Timsbury, UK (small town) and from the Hayesfield School in Bath, UK (medium town) were involved by Boundaries in online dialogues only. Therefore, information on diversity is restricted to ISCED Level (Level 1 and 2 for Timsbury participants; Level 2 and 3 in Hayesfield School) and to gender (Timsbury 4 male/3female, Hayesfield School 63 female).

PYE worked with 73 children and young people in four separate spaces, three Youth Centres and one Primary School. Some 58% of the participants were male (42) with 42% female (31).

Of the primary school aged children, some 29 were aged between 9 and 10 years. 22 of these children were from ethnic minorities, mostly Asian backgrounds. These children were at ISCED Level 1.

The work within Youth Centres involved 44 young people aged from 15 to 21 years, with the mean age being 17 years. Within The Winch Youth Centre in north London, all 12 of the participants were from ethnic backgrounds, mostly Afro-Caribbean. The Pembury Centre was the base for one set of WYRED activities and 3 of the 7 participants were from ethnic backgrounds. The NCS Community Centre in Cambridge was the host organisation for 25 young people, 8 of whom were from ethnic backgrounds. These participants were all at ISCED Levels 3 to 4.

3 Conclusions

Inclusion was an integral part of our work. Diversity of children and young people has been given a voice in WYRED. The project met its objectives not only regarding the transparent documentation of diversity by the inclusion reports, but also in the numerous and diverse topics selected for research activities, projects and artefacts, the online conversations and

fortnights – of course not to speak of the wealth of the WYRED participants in regard to diversity.

All partners in WYRED were and are committed to an understanding of diversity being normal and which has nothing to do with achieving some form of predefined “normality”. Diversity was naturally given due to the cultural differences within the Western European partners and the partner countries Israel and Turkey. These differences turned out to be an important factor for the development of the Inclusion questionnaire. The questionnaire during the three cycles was and will remain a living document after the official end of the project. Based on cycle 3 statistics, another adaptation was implemented in December 2019. Though, already in cycle 1 it had turned out to be a self-running process and proved its usability for the statistics-based description of the IQ participants. During the three cycles we had a stable rate of IQ participants ranging from 47 % to 55 %. This can be regarded as satisfactory.

The platform statistics – as already stated – do not tell the whole story as the analyses provided by the consortium partners does in giving insights into the diversity of the 1670 WYRED young people engaged in the project.

Summing up, the objectives according to inclusion in WYRED as defined in the proposal can be answered as follows:

- Is the full richness of young people represented in WYRED?

WYRED performed very well in engaging a big range of diverse young people in its activities. Age being closely related to educational level, migration, ethnicity, religion, sexual orientation, regionality, disabilities were sufficiently covered as related to the benchmarks defined in D.2.1. However, more females than males completed the questionnaire, which is also reflected in the share of females and males participating in total. It can be assumed that this is related to the involvement of gender biased topics of study, respectively faculties or organisations. Although the consortium was aware of this issue, it evidently was not possible to reach the equal share of male and female participants aimed at. Possibly as it would have meant to exclude females from taking part in WYRED. Notwithstanding it was easier for example to enhance the participation rate of participants aged 10 to 14 years from cycle 2 to 3.

- Did WYRED assure inclusion for marginalised young people?

It was not only that diversity in WYRED was given to a high extend, but also criteria connected to marginalisation like having a low socio-economic status (21,04 % of our participants) were sufficiently covered. This factor is closely connected to education, as socio-economically disadvantaged students are almost three times more likely than socio-economically advantaged students not to reach basic science literacy levels (OECD, 2016). Also, the influence of social status on health and life expectancy is regularly confirmed by epidemiological studies⁴. Cultural differences are extremely important for defining marginalisation in the partner countries. Whereas homosexuality in Western European Countries (about 5 % of IQ participants) finds its way to marriages, in Turkey asking about sexual orientation or gender fluidity in schools is problematic. Religion is most important in Northern Ireland, and Migration plays a big role in Austria (approx. 11 % in total). This gives the impression that the political systems in their history and current states are playing an important role in this context. Not to speak of ethnicity, telling us that 12 % of the WYRED participants on the platform can be subsumed to a minority group in their specific countries. Further, it must be considered, that the factors leading to marginalisation are interrelated – discrimination never comes alone as we know from the gender theories of intersectionality (Crenshaw, 1989; Walgenbach, 2013; Knapp, 2008).

- Has attention been ensured to inclusion in all the aspects of the work?

In order to ensure transparency on inclusion during the course of the project, continuous information on the status quo was given to the partners, be it in the form of the annual reports or in form of presentations and discussions at the project meetings.

⁴https://www.rki.de/DE/Content/Gesundheitsmonitoring/Themen/Sozialer_Status/sozialer_status_node.html;jsessionid=F95F53B3CA83128B9DAA98654AFEB267.1_cid372

Unconscious assumptions about migrants, heterosexual persons, low educated people, people stemming from rural regions, people adhering to a different religion or being disabled can never be totally avoided. Nevertheless, the consortiums' clear understanding of diversity as being a normal and wanted aspect of the activities, has set the course for us. Gender as being one of the most important diversity criteria for example played an important role in the participants' works: 18 out of the 182 projects are dedicated to this topic, like "Gender based idioms", "Image of women online", "Gender (in)equality", "Male emotions online", etc. Also, the fortnights "Gender Stereotype and Gender equality on the internet" and "Gender stereotypes – The way out" attracted numerous young people, as well the 2nd day of the Online-Festival, which mainly focussed on gender differences in STEM (Science, Technology, Education and Mathematics).

Evaluation consistently showed that young people perceived WYRED as supportive and that they were given a voice. This not only accounts for participants in general, but also for the marginalized groups within WYRED.

WYRED was a self-developing project in consistently adapting its methodology to the learnings of previous activities. This is especially true for the requirements of the different educational levels just considering that we were working with Primary School pupils as well as with University students. WYRED by itself is diverse, driven by the diversity of the participants and the big variety of their activities, be it on the platform or in face to face activities. WYRED in its diversity will remain to be a self-developing project in the future in further realizing its goals and experiences sustainably in the WYRED Association.

4 References

- Abdul- Hussain, S., & Baig, S. (2009). *Diversity in Supervision, Coaching und Beratung*. Wien: Facultas Verlags- und Buchhandels AG.
- Crenshaw, K. (1989). Demarginalizing the Intersection of Race and Sex: A Black Feminist Critique of Antidiscrimination Doctrine, Feminist Theory, and Antiracist Politics. *The University of Chicago Legal Forum*, 139–167.
- European Commission. (2016). *Compulsory Education in Europe 2016-2017* (Eurydice Facts and Figures). Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.
- Eurostat. (2017). *Migration and migrant population statistics*. Abgerufen von http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Migration_and_migrant_population_statistics#Migrant_population
- García-Holgado, A., & García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2018). WYRED Platform, the ecosystem for the young people. Paper presented at the HCI International 2018, Las Vegas, NV, USA.
<https://youtu.be/TRDjN5boky8>
- García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2017). WYRED Project. *Education in the Knowledge Society*, 18(3), 7-14.
doi:10.14201/eks2017183714
- García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2018). WYRED una plataforma para dar la voz a los jóvenes sobre la influencia de la tecnología en la sociedad actual. Un enfoque de ciencia ciudadana. Paper presented at the II Congreso Internacional de Tendencias en Innovación Educativa (CITIE 2018), Arequipa (Perú).
- García-Peñalvo, F. J., & Durán-Escudero, J. (2017). Interaction design principles in WYRED platform. In P. Zaphiris & A. Ioannou (Eds.), *Learning and Collaboration Technologies. Technology in Education. 4th International Conference, LCT 2017*. Held as Part of HCI International 2017,

Vancouver, BC, Canada, July 9–14, 2017. Proceedings, Part II (pp. 371-381). Switzerland: Springer International Publishing.

García-Peñalvo, F. J., & García-Holgado, A. (2019). WYRED, a platform to give young people the voice on the influence of technology in today's society. A citizen science approach. In K. O. Villalba-Condori, F. J. García-Peñalvo, J. Lavonen, & M. Zapata-Ros (Eds.), Proceedings of the II Congreso Internacional de Tendencias e Innovación Educativa – CITIE 2018 (Arequipa, Perú, November 26-30, 2018) (pp. 128-141). Aachen, Germany: CEUR-WS.org.

García-Peñalvo, F. J., García-Holgado, A., Vázquez-Ingelmo, A., & Seoane-Pardo, A. M. (2018). Usability test of WYRED Platform. In P. Zaphiris & A. Ioannou (Eds.), Learning and Collaboration Technologies. Design, Development and Technological Innovation. 5th International Conference, LCT 2018, Held as Part of HCI International 2018, Las Vegas, NV, USA, July 15-20, 2018, Proceedings, Part I (pp. 73-84). Cham, Switzerland: Springer.

García-Peñalvo, F. J., & Kearney, N. A. (2016). Networked youth research for empowerment in digital society. The WYRED project. In F. J. García-Peñalvo (Ed.), Proceedings of the Fourth International Conference on Technological Ecosystems for Enhancing Multiculturality (TEEM'16) (Salamanca, Spain, November 2-4, 2016) (pp. 3-9). New York, NY, USA: ACM.

García-Peñalvo, F. J., Vázquez-Ingelmo, A., & García-Holgado, A. (2019). Study of the Usability of the WYRED Ecosystem Using Heuristic Evaluation. In P. Zaphiris & A. Ioannou (Eds.), Learning and Collaboration Technologies. Design, Experiences. 6th International Conference, LCT 2019, Held as Part of the 21st HCI International Conference, HCII 2019, Orlando, FL, USA, July 26–31, 2019. Proceedings, Part I (pp. 50-63). Cham, Switzerland: Springer Nature.

García-Peñalvo, F. J., Vázquez-Ingelmo, A., García-Holgado, A., & Seoane-Pardo, A. M. (2019). Analyzing the usability of the WYRED Platform with undergraduate students to improve its features. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 18(3), 455-468. doi:10.1007/s10209-019-00672-z

Griffiths, D., Kearney, N. A., García-Peñalvo, F. J., Seoane-Pardo, A. M., Cicala, F., Gojkovic, T., . . .

Zauchner-Studnicka, S. (2017). Children and Young People Today: Initial Insights from the WYRED Project. European Union: WYRED Consortium. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/6unxmD>

Knapp, G.-A. (2008). „Intersectionality“ - ein neues Paradigma der Geschlechterforschung? In R. Casale & B. Rendtorff (Hrsg.), *Was kommt nach der Genderforschung? Zur Zukunft feministischer Theoriebildung*. Bielefeld: transcript Verlag.

Europäische Kommission (Hrsg.). (2016). *Urban Europe: statistics on cities, towns and suburbs* (2016 edition). Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.

Loden, M., & Rosener, J. B. (1991). *Workforce America!: managing employee diversity as a vital resource*. Homewood, Ill: Business One Irwin.

Lutz, H., Herrera Vivar, M. T., & Supik, L. (Hrsg.). (2013). *Fokus Intersektionalität: Bewegungen und Verortungen eines vielschichtigen Konzeptes* (2. Aufl.). Wiesbaden: Springer VS.

OECD (2016). *Sozioökonomischer Status, Schülerleistungen und Einstellungen gegenüber Naturwissenschaften*. Retrieved from: <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/docserver/9789264267879-10-de.pdf?expires=1573899025&id=id&accname=guest&checksum=0E2B8F53067D82D34C437870DA379F36>, {11.05.2019}.

Statistical Office of the European Communities. (2015). *Being young in Europe today: 2015 edition*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Abgerufen von <http://dx.publications.europa.eu/10.2785/59267>

Walgenbach, K. (2013). Postscriptum: Intersektionalität - Offenheit, interne Kontroversen und Komplexität als Ressourcen eines gemeinsamen Orientierungsrahmens. In H. Lutz, M. T. Herrera Vivar, & L. Supik (Hrsg.), *Fokus Intersektionalität: Bewegungen und Verortungen eines vielschichtigen Konzeptes* (2. Aufl., S. 265–279). Wiesbaden: Springer VS.

Zauchner-Studnicka, S. (2017). Inclusion Criteria. WP2_D2.1 v2. EU: WYRED Consortium.

Zauchner-Studnicka, S. (2018a). Inclusion Report 1. WP2_D2.2 Version 3. EU: WYRED Consortium.

Zauchner-Studnicka, S. (2018b). Inclusion Report 2. WP2_D2.3. EU: WYRED Consortium.

5 Glossary of Terms

Culture

A social system of meaning and custom that is developed by a group of people. These groups are distinguished by a set of unspoken rules that shape values, beliefs, habits, patterns of thinking, behavior and styles of communication.

Disability

Physical or mental impairment, the perception of a physical or mental impairment, or a history of having had a physical or mental impairment that limits one or more major life activities.

Diversity

Psychological, physical, and social differences that occur among all individuals; including but not limited to race, ethnicity, nationality, religion, socioeconomic status, education, marital status, language, age, gender, sexual orientation, mental or physical ability, and learning styles. A diverse group, community, or organization is one in which a variety of social and cultural characteristics exist.

Diversity Management

A management model which describes the measures leading to acknowledgement and valuing of differences as well as regarded to be useful in an organization.

Equality

Evenly distributed access to resources and opportunity necessary for a safe and healthy life; uniform distribution of access to ensure fairness.

Ethnicity

Similarly to the term culture, an ethnic group or ethnicity is a category of people who identify with each other based on similarities such as common ancestral, language, social, cultural or national experiences.

Equity

The guarantee of fair treatment, access, opportunity, and advancement while at the same time striving to identify and eliminate barriers that have prevented the full participation of some groups. The principle of equity acknowledges that there are historically underserved and under-represented populations and that fairness regarding these unbalanced conditions is needed to assist equality in the provision of effective opportunities to all groups.

Gender

The socially constructed ideas about the behavior, actions and roles of a specific sex; differentiated from sex, a system of classification based on biological and physical differences, such as primary and secondary sexual characteristics.

Inclusion

Creation of environments in which any individual or group can be and feel welcomed, respected, supported, and valued, to be able to fully participate. An inclusive and welcoming climate embraces differences and offers respect in words and actions for all people.

Marginalization

The placement of minority groups and cultures outside mainstream society. All that varies from the norm of the dominant culture is devalued and at times perceived as deviant and regressive.

Migration

The movement of a person or a group of persons, either across an international border, or within a state. It includes the migration of refugees and displaced persons, economic migrants, and persons moving for other purposes, including family reunification.

Norm

An ideal standard that is binding upon the members of a group and serves to guide, control, or regulate power and acceptable behavior.

Stereotype

A positive or negative set of beliefs held by an individual about the characteristics of a certain group.

Sexual orientation

An enduring pattern of romantic or sexual attraction (or a combination of these) to persons of the opposite sex or gender, the same sex or gender, or to both sexes or more than one gender. These attractions are generally subsumed under heterosexuality, homosexuality and bisexuality while asexuality (the lack of sexual attraction to others) is sometimes identified as the fourth category.

Transgender

An umbrella term for people whose gender identity differs from their birth gender. Transgender can refer to a range of groups including transsexual people and those who see themselves as not clearly fitting into a male or female identity. Transgender people may or may not alter their bodies hormonally and/or surgically.

6 Appendix

6.1 Inclusion Questionnaire

Gender

Which gender do you attribute to yourself?

Version 1 Used by all partners for participants aged < 18 years

- female
- male
- male

Version 2 Used in all partner countries except Turkey for participants aged >18 years

- female
- male
- not mentioned above (if you wish, please specify):
- no answer

Age

Your year of birth: List starting with 1945

Educational or Work Background

What is your highest level of education? → List of the ISCED levels (International Standard Classification of Education):

List of ISCED levels (Explanations of levels adapted to partners' countries)

- ISCED 0: Early childhood education
- ISCED 1: Primary education,
- ISCED 2: Lower secondary education,
- ISCED 3: Upper secondary education,
- ISCED 4: Post-secondary non-tertiary education,
- ISCED 5: Short-cycle tertiary education,
- ISCED 6: Bachelors' or equivalent level, ISCED 7: Masters' or equivalent level,
- ISCED 8: Doctors or equivalent level

Currently, are you student in formal education?

Yes:

No: → What are you doing in the moment?

- non-formal training,
- internship,
- employed,
- self-employed,
- unemployed

Socio-Economic Status

Parents' Educational Status

What is the highest school level attained by your mother? → List of the ISCED categories

- I can't answer this question

What is the highest school level attained by your father? → List of the ISCED categories

- I can't answer this question

Geographic Location

Where do you live?

- Village/rural community (< 5,000 inhabitants)
- Small town (5,000-20,000 inhabitants)
- Medium town (20,000-100,000 inhabitants)
- Big town (> 100,000 inhabitants)

Where do you study or work?

- Village/rural community (< 5,000 inhabitants)
- Small town (5,000-20,000 inhabitants)
- Medium town (20,000-100,000 inhabitants)
- Big town (> 100,000 inhabitants)

Migration

Which language is mainly spoken in your family? → List of languages

Where were you born? → List of countries

Where was your father born? → List of countries

- I can't answer this question

Where was your mother born? → List of countries

- I can't answer this question

Ethnic/National Background

Do you identify with an ethnic/national group?

An ethnic group is a group of people who identify with each other based on similarities such as common ancestry, language, history, society, culture or nation. An ethnic group could for example be "Italian", "Austrian Croat", "Romani", "Syrian", "Maghrebi" "Arabic", "Afro-Caribbean" "Indian", "Kurd" or "Irish Traveller".

- Yes
- No
- No Answer

If yes: *What is your ethnic/national group?* → What is your ethnic group? (open question)

Religious Background

What is your religious background?

- Catholic
- Protestant
- Orthodox
- Muslim
- Jewish
- Atheistic/Not-believing
- Other
- No answer

Do you consider yourself an active part of this group?

- Yes
- No
- No answer

Disability

Do you have any long-term illness, health problem or disability which limits your daily activities?

- No
- Yes
- No answer

Sexual Orientation

If applicable: (depending on country and participant's age)

Do you perceive yourself as being ...

- Heterosexual?
- Homosexual?
- Bisexual?
- No answer

6.2 Inclusion Template

PARTNER	
Participating Organisation	
Dates of Participation Mont/Year - month/Year	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Place (number)	

<p>Village/rural community (<5,000 inhabitants) Small town (5,000-20,000 inhabitants) Medium town (20,000-100,000 inhabitants) Big town (> 100,000 inhabitants)</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Age-Group (number): <=10, <=15, <=20, <=25, <=30 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gender Female/male/other 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Migrant 1st Generation (number) Participants born in another county 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Migrant 2nd Generation (number) Participants' parents born in another country 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ISCED Level 1-8 (number per group) <p>ISCED 1 - Primary education (Primary Schools: Key stage 1 and key stage 2), ISCED 2 - Lower secondary education (Secondary Schools: Key stage 3), ISCED 3 - Upper secondary education (Secondary schools, Secondary vocational education & Combined school and workplace courses, Further HEI Access courses), ISCED 4 - Post-secondary non-tertiary education, ISCED 5 - Short-cycle tertiary education (Higher/Further education institutions: 2 years), ISCED 6 - Bachelors' or equivalent level (Higher/Further education institutions: 3 years), ISCED 7 - Masters' or equivalent level (Higher/Further education institutions: 5 years), ISCED 8 - Doctors or equivalent level</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Status (number) Formal Training, nonformal training, internship, employed, unemployed 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SEC Socio-Economic Status (numbers) Estimation in relation to county: Low, Medium, High 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ethnic Background (number) An ethnic or national group is a group of people who identify with each other based on similarities such as common language, culture, nation, society, ancestry or history. An ethnic group could for example be "Italian", "Irish", "Welsh", "Sami", "Syrian", "Romani", or Kurd". 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chronical illness or disability (Number) 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Religion (number of active participants/religious form) 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sexual orientation (number heterosexual/Homosexual) 	